

Reconstruction of History in Lawrence Norfolk's *John Saturnall's Feast*

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Abstract

This article focuses on the implication of historical narratives in Lawrence Norfolk's *John Saturnall's Feast*. Stephen Greenblatt's "New Historicism" is constructed on the parallel reading of literary and non-literary texts, usually from the same historical period. Lawrence Norfolk is a British author of historical fiction who incorporates historical elements into his works. One of his works, *John Saturnall's Feast*, exclusively highlights British history, especially in the period of war. His historical narratives are highly imaginative, which are mingled with historical artefacts in his novel. He represented the historical events, geographical descriptions, cultural narratives, and political implications throughout the historical narratives. He also presented some historical figures in his novel to create a real sense for the readers. His natural descriptions enslaved the readers along with the historical senses, and his imaginative narratives provided anaesthetic pleasures. This article mainly attempts to explore how Lawrence Norfolk reconstructs the historical context, the political context, the social context, and the cultural context in the selected novel.

Key words: War, Political, Social, Cultural, Historical

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New Historicism is an approach to literary criticism and literary theory based on the premise that a literary work should be viewed as a product of its time, place, and circumstances of its composition rather than an isolated creation of genius. It is a movement that came into existence in 1980. Literary critic, theorist, and scholar Stephen Greenblatt coined the term "New Historicism," which considers literary history as a record of a cultural product.

New Historicists take political and intellectual history as a background to give an account of the subject matter in literature at a particular time and place. They concentrate on the literary work's fragments of social experiences. The facts of the past are central to the new historicism. New Historicists interpret these facts from their points of view and create a new history. Sometimes history is misrepresented in the past and represented in different documents as texts. Writers shape subjects that shape culture. Power was constantly flowing through the various discourses on religion, science, fashion, law, and so on.

According to Foucault, all discourse is socially constructed and maintained by power. The New Historicism deconstructs the traditional differences between history and literature, and therefore, history is another form of literature. New Historicism gives importance to the term "thick description". It examines the ways to find out the meanings of cultural production and social conventions.

Lawrence Norfolk is one of the twenty-first century's most ambitious historical novelists, above all a painter of vast historical panoramas. His work demonstrates a strong emphasis on the visual aspect, which makes him different from other major historical novelists of recent decades who have turned their attention to the past because that is where they found striking stories to be used in the narrative.

One of his works, *John Saturnall's Feast*, can even be read as a provocative alternative to the historical picture of English literature and culture in the seventeenth century. Norfolk's story is an interesting counterpoint to the dominant Puritan discourse represented by authors like Milton and Bunyan. From this perspective, it is considered a fascinating book to learn about because it crosses the boundaries of fiction and enters cultural history.

The novel is titled after the name of the protagonist, John Saturnall. The word "Saturnall" is derived from the words "Saturn" in Rome and "Saturnus" in Latin. Saturnus is the god of agriculture, especially the god of sowing or seed. The novel starts with the Roman Myth of Saturn, in which Saturn is identified with the Greek Cronus. Exiled from Olympus by Zeus, he ruled Latium in a happy and innocent golden age, where he taught his people agriculture and other peaceful arts. In myth, he was the father of Picus.

Saturnalia is Saturn's great festival, which became one of the most popular festivals in Roman times. It was originally celebrated on December 17 and later extended to seven days. It was the happiest time of the year, when all work and business were put on hold; slaves were given temporary freedom to say and do whatever they pleased; certain moral restrictions were relaxed; and presents were freely exchanged.

The novel deals with such a myth of the Romans and also mentions the everyday feast they made for Saturnall in which there was no distinction between men and women and everyone was treated equally. This reference appears in various places throughout the novel in various forms, such as in John's mother's book, oral stories told by the majority of the characters, and a sculpture in Buckland's Manor House.

He watched her open the book. Once again he looked down at the goblet filled with words, the three scripts written over each other. His mother's fingers brushed the vines that curled about the cup. 'This was the first garden,' she said. 'That was Eden,' John told her. 'They called it that later.' She tapped the page. 'In the beginning every green thing grew here. Every creature thrived.

The first men and women lived in amity together. They knew no hunger or pain. Saturnus's people kept the Feast.' (Norfolk 88)

The author moved the story from Roman myth to Milton's paradise lost by mentioning that after the departure of the Romans from the Buckland Wood, the place was later called the "Garden of Eden," where everything green grows and where the first man and woman lead a harmonious life. All of these things are revealed to the protagonist through the book and the oral story of his mother.

He pointed out Britain's history with these references in the novel, ranging from Roman myth to Milton's paradise. He represents the Roman invasion of Britain through the following of Roman myths in Britain. When the Romans leave Britain, puritanism takes its place, which was symbolised by Milton's Paradise Lost, that is, by the mentioning of the first man and woman in the garden of Eden.

After the death of his mother, the protagonist moved to the manor house of Buckland, where he came to know about the lives of the Lordships of small places who were under the king of England. Even the manor house has many guards and teams with various coloured uniforms who work in the house's various teams under the supervision of the chief for each team. Their lifestyle, food, shelter, and everything else changes depending on their position in that house.

At the manor house, they have their own set of rules that must be followed at all costs. Only the chiefs of the various teams are permitted to deliver information to the manor, even indirectly through the assistance of higher officials who are next to the manor. Employees should not even raise their heads to see or communicate with their superiors. They should keep their heads down and listen to their orders. If someone doesn't follow these rules and is mischievous or against them, they will be sent to the outcast station for cruel punishment. This is one of the customs that were followed in the manor house.

The rulers of the various territories are subject to the lordship of Charles I, King of England, Scotland, and Ireland. They signed an agreement in the name of God with the king in which women were not permitted to be heirs of vale and were also prohibited from doing certain things that men in the kingdom were permitted to do.

As God's Ministers directed me, and for the sake of his Son Jesus Christ, so I swear: that we and all our Descendants do keep these Lands and Hearths and hold them for our Sovereign King. Let no Woman take Fire to the Hearth, nor tend the Vale's Fires, nor give Nourishment save she be bid, nor rule in the Vale, nor hold Rights to a Virgate of Land, nor keep Retainers or Servants lest these Lands be surrendered again to the Enemies of Our Lord (109-10)

This agreement made Sir William Fremantle helpless because he didn't have a son to rule after him. Though his only daughter, Lady Lucretia, has a majority, she can't be crowned

under those agreements which made Sir William give her in the hands of marriage to Piers Callock, Lord of Forham and Artois, a drunkard who doesn't even have the courage of a man and is unfit to rule the kingdom. Being a male born into higher possession, he became the heir of Buckland, Forham, and Artois.

It vividly depicts the social, political, and cultural context of the 17th century. Though the king or ruler must be concerned with the welfare of the people and kingdom, they did not consider the lives of those who would suffer under the drunkard's rule. They simply followed their rules and agreement in order to save themselves and keep their family safe.

Then the story deals with the civil war that broke out between King Charles I and the Parliament, who were unhappy with the ruling and the rules of the King. "Word was passed down the column that it was Parliament's army. Fairfax was its commander and Waller and Cromwell were his generals" (275). Though Sir William was opposed to the war, he was in a position to follow the king's words, so he moved to the battleground with his soldiers to support his king.

Sir William entrusted Buckland to his daughter in order to protect it at any cost. She made a promise to her father to protect their land, and she was even willing to die for it while her father, fiance, and higher officials were fighting. She took the ladyship of Buckland until the end of the war. Even though she could only eat one meal a day to survive, she faced all of the challenges and kept her promise to protect their land.

The soldiers in the camp were not provided with adequate food and shelter, but the king and ministers were well cared for, even when the stock hold was merely empty during the war. At the end of the war, power was transferred to Parliament. When Oliver Cromwell came to power, he was strongly opposed to all the luxurious things that the king enjoyed in the name of the higher chair:

Armed with Flintlock and Bible, he did preach an unfamiliar Lesson to the Nation. That there was no Christmas, nor May-feast, nor Hocktide, nor Feast or Fast. Indeed he eschewed all such Luxuries. Then Oysters were mixed with Crumbs and Dukes did seek their Dinners in the Hedgerows or they fled to the Garrets of Paris. Find here, therefore, a Feast for that One who would have None, calling it a Papist Invention, and remember in these Dishes those Times when a pickled Fish and a Bowl of Gruel was a Benison for a Lord and a Drop-apple was Supper enough for the fattest Bishop.... (297)

He brings about many changes in the lives of the ministers and also in the common people. Though many lead a happy life, the supporters of the king who were defeated are waiting for the turn of the king to rule because they are used to it and have made it their happy life, so they are unable to accept a normal life without any luxuries.

The novel ends with the king's rule of Charles II, who came into power after the death of Cromwell. He brought back all the luxurious items for the higher officials of the kingdom. It clearly brings out the view of life from the invasion of Rome to the rule of Charles II after the parliament in the civil war. The author used Buckland as an icon to portray the social, cultural, and political changes in the history of the 17th century. In other words, he reconstructed history with his artistic talent in this novel, *John Saturnall's Feast*, which is easy to dwell on and understand because there aren't many complications in the history of the period.

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